

OWPT2025 : Oral Presentation

📅 Thu. Apr 24, 2025 9:30 AM - 10:30 AM JST | Thu. Apr 24, 2025 12:30 AM - 1:30 AM UTC 🏠 416+417
(Conference Center)

Session 6

Session Chair: Makoto Miyoshi (Nagoya Institute of Tech.)

9:30 AM - 10:00 AM JST | 12:30 AM - 1:00 AM UTC

[OWPT6-01(Invited)] RePowerSiC: High-Efficiency High-Power Laser Conversion Systems Based on SiC for Space Applications

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The RePowerSiC project can open a path to high-power energy transmission technology for space applications. We aim to develop novel ultra-efficient SiC Optical Power Converters for in-space energy transmission in the range of kW/cm² with efficiencies higher than 80% at extremely large distance. Preliminary results show that SiC-based OPCs can greatly improve the efficiency of the technology, increasing one order of magnitude the power density.

RePowerSiC: High-Efficiency High-Power Laser Conversion Systems Based on SiC for Space Applications

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Abstract: The RePowerSiC project can open a path to high-power energy transmission technology for space applications. We aim to develop novel ultra-efficient SiC Optical Power Converters (OPCs) for in-space energy transmission in the range of kW/cm² with efficiencies higher than 80% at extremely large distance. The OPCs are based on SiC polytypes, wide bandgap materials with high radiation resistance and thermal conductivity. These materials minimize the series resistance and intrinsic entropic losses of the photovoltaic receiver. Preliminary results show that SiC-based OPCs can greatly improve the efficiency of the technology, increasing one order of magnitude the power density, and broaden the range of HPLT applications.

1. Introduction

There is an increasing interest in space activities from governments and private companies, including new orbit satellite services for Earth such as global positioning systems and communications; planet exploration; in-space manufacturing and other novel activities. In most of these applications, providing energy securely and flexibly to improve spacecraft mobility is fundamental. Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) technology is an essential approach to enable future space applications. It allows the separation of power collection, conversion and transmission, offering the following advantages: i) a reduced complexity of the design of the spacecraft, thus minimising their costs and technical risks, ii) a reduced weight of the total system and iii) the possibility of extending their range of operation in environments with limited sun availability (e.g. lunar nights, deep space)¹.

For space applications are valid only two WPT technologies²: Microwave Power Transmission (MPT), and Optical Power Transmission (OPT), which uses a monochromatic light source, e.g. a laser, to transfer power, see Fig 1. The key difference between these two technologies is their wavelength ranges to transfer energy. While most MPT rely on 0.12 - 0.05 m, the current OPT uses near infrared frequencies (0.8 - 2.5 μ m). These five orders of magnitude differences in the wavelength are the key element that determines i) the size of the emitting and receiving structures and ii) the energy density that can be transmitted. The lower wavelength values used in OPT provide this technology with the following advantages compared to MPT: i) a much smaller diameter of the emitter and receiver, ii) the capability to handle high energy densities, and iii) a narrow focus of the beam, which are critical for space applications.

2. RePowerSiC project

It is a Pathfinder Challenge project funded by the European Commission under the In-Space Energy Harvesting for Innovative Space Applications call, started in October 2024. RePowerSiC will establish a new highly

efficient, cost-effective, High-Power OPT (HP-OPT) technology in the EU for space applications. This is a high-risk, high-gain technology, still in an early development stage, attracting huge interest, currently being mainly applied to power systems over fibre. Substantial efforts are needed for the technology to succeed in space applications, i.e. increasing the efficiency (Eff) and the amount of power density that can be transferred, currently limited to ≈ 100 W/cm². For this paradigm shift, the development of a new generation ultra-efficiency OPC, suitable for transferring power in the order of kilowatts to extremely large distances, is crucial. Implementing our technology in space systems will expand the range of operations, reduce their weight, increase their lifetimes and make their batteries smaller or unnecessary.

Fig 1 Scheme of a HP-OPT system

2.1 SiC based materials

SiC polytypes 4H, 6H and 3C, with energy gaps of 3.23 eV, 3.02 eV and 2.36 eV respectively can revolutionise HP-OPT³. Theoretically, fewer photons are needed for the same power density for these high bandgap materials, reducing ohmic losses and paving the way for efficient conversion at ultra-high power densities. In addition, SiC presents high thermal stability, radiation resistance, and high dielectric strength⁴, making it appealing for space applications.

2.2 Optical Power Converter

In this project, we aim to model, fabricate and characterise 4H, 6H and 3C SiC-based OPCs using the horizontal (hOPC) and vertical (vOPC) architectures, see Fig 2. The vOPC reduces shadowing and series resistance-related losses. For the modelling, we use Silvaco Atlas⁵ and in-house-built iterative optimisation algorithms, including machine learning techniques. Once the best working polytype was established for each space

application case, we use it as the base material for the vOPC architecture.

Fig 2 2D scheme of the hOPC (a) and vOPC (b) architectures.

The Eff for these modelled devices are presented in Fig 3. For reference, we compare them with two state-of-the-art GaAs-based experimental devices, whose Eff are 68.9% at 11 W cm^{-2} (hOPC) and 66. % at 150 W cm^{-2} (5-cell VEHSA)⁷. It is expected that the larger the bandgap energy, the higher the Eff that these devices could achieve. However, at 1 W cm^{-2} , the three SiC polytype hOPCs present the same Eff around 78%. This is due to losses related to the wavelength selection to achieve similar optical absorption coefficients, and other material properties. As the laser power density increases, the 3C hOPC achieves Eff of 82.1% at 10 and 100 W cm^{-2} , which is 13.2% higher than the best experimental hOPC and 15.8% higher than the best experimental OPC (5-cell VEHSA) at high laser power densities. The 4H hOPC experiences a very slow Eff growth with Pin due to its high effective density of state values, and the 6H experiences a quick Eff decay due to high Auger losses (higher Auger coefficient). At 1000 W cm^{-2} , all hOPCs suffer from series resistance losses. As the 3C-SiC is the best performance polytype, we implemented it in the vOPC architecture. It performs similarly to the 3C hOPC at low Pin values, but as the laser power density increases, it does not show series resistance losses, achieving impressive 86.6% and 87.4% Eff at 100 and 1000 W cm^{-2} .

Once we have established the optimum design, including thermal management, that maximises system Eff, OPC will be fabricated and characterised. Finally, the complete HPOT system will be validated in laboratory conditions similar to those in outer space.

4. Conclusion

In RePowerSiC project we explore the suitability of high power optical transmission technology for space applications using SiC polytypes (high-band gap materials), and novel architectures. Preliminary modelling results show that the 3C, 4H and 6H SiC polytypes using the horizontal optical photovoltaic converter (hOPC) architecture perform around $\approx 10\%$ better than the current GaAs-based state-of-the-art at low power densities. As the 3C was the best performance polytype, we also included

it in the vertical optical photovoltaic converter (vOPC) architecture, which notices no losses due to series resistance and achieves up to 87.4% efficiency at 1000 W cm^{-2} .

Fig 3 Efficiency vs laser power density of the proposed SiC hOPCs and vOPCs, and other state-of-the-art devices^{6,7}.

Acknowledgment

RePowerSiC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under grant agreement N 101160868. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the EIC. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Work supported by the Xunta de Galicia - Consellería de Cultura, Educación, Formación Profesional e Universidades (Centro de investigación de Galicia accreditation 2024-2027 ED431G-2023/04 and Reference Competitive Group accreditation ED431C-2022/016) and the European Union (European Regional Development Fund - ERDF/EU).

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